

Leveraging Grain Boundary Effects for Nanostructured Electrode Layers in Symmetric Solid Oxide Fuel Cells

Federico Baiutti,* Francesco Chiabrera, Marlene Anzengruber, Kosova Kreka, Juande Sirvent, Lluís Yedra, Fjorelo Buzi, Macej Oskar Liedke, Andrea Cavallaro, Albert Carmona Zuazo, Sonia Estradé, Maik Butterling, Eric Hirschmann, Andreas Wagner, Ainara Aguadero, Francisca Peiró, and Albert Tarancon

While grain boundary engineering is attracting great interest as a potential strategy to fabricate highly electrochemically active materials, open questions remain in relation to the fundamental mechanisms of local property enhancement as well as to the potential technological impact of such nanostructuring strategies. In this paper, the ability to turn a predominantly electronic conductor into an excellent mixed-ionic electronic conductor by grain boundary doping is demonstrated for nanocrystalline films of lanthanum chromite. A four-orders-of-magnitude increase in the oxygen diffusion coefficient at grain boundaries is observed, and related to local chemical changes. It is shown that grain boundary effects can be effectively exploited for technological purposes by fabricating a proof-of-concept symmetric solid oxide cell based on lanthanum chromite film electrodes. The cell is operated under reversible gas feeding conditions, exhibiting electrode self-healing characteristics. The results provide new insights on the fundamental aspects of fast grain boundary oxygen diffusion and validate grain boundary engineering as a technologically relevant strategy for the realization of solid oxide cells with enhanced performance.

defect accumulation at interface cores^[4,5] have demonstrated potential for inducing local modifications in the oxygen vacancy concentration and mobility,^[6] as well as the surface chemistry.^[7] In the mesoscopic regime, these phenomena may become predominant over the bulk behavior and can potentially be exploited for achieving enhanced kinetics of oxygen reduction reaction (ORR). A number of different “interface-dominated” thin film architectures have shown excellent promise for enhancing ORR: They comprise epitaxial films,^[8] multilayers,^[9] and nanocrystalline materials with maximized grain boundary (GB) densities.^[10] The latter in particular have received attention in recent years, also in light of a simpler fabrication that facilitates the potential implementation in real systems.^[11] In (La, Sr)MnO₃ (LSM) for example, a relatively sluggish bulk diffusion kinetics for oxygen (<10⁻¹⁵ cm²

1. Introduction

Thin film nanoengineering provides an avenue for the realization of materials with enhanced performance. In the context of high-temperature electrodes for solid oxide cells (SOCs), phenomena such as elastic strain,^[1] formation of space-charge layers,^[2,3] or

s⁻¹ at $T < 950$ °C) is counteracted by 2–3 orders of magnitude faster GB diffusion depending on temperature and bulk stoichiometry.^[10,12,13] By using simple thin film approaches, nanocolumnar LSM has been fabricated where such an effect is maximized resulting in strongly enhanced ORR kinetics.^[13–15]

F. Baiutti, F. Chiabrera, M. Anzengruber, K. Kreka, J. Sirvent, F. Buzi, A. Carmona Zuazo, A. Tarancon
Catalonia Institute for Energy Research (IREC)
Jardins de Les Dones de Negre 1, Sant Adrià del Besòs, Barcelona 08930, Spain
E-mail: fbaiutti@irec.cat

L. Yedra, S. Estradé, F. Peiró
Laboratory of Electron Nanoscopies (LENS)
Micro-Nanotechnology and Nanoscopies for Electronic and Electrophotonic Devices (MIND)
Department of Electronics and Biomedical Engineering and Institute of Nanoscience and Nanotechnology (IN2UB)
University of Barcelona
C/ Martí i Franquès 1, Barcelona 08028, Spain
M. O. Liedke, M. Butterling, E. Hirschmann, A. Wagner
Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf
Institute of Radiation Physics
01328 Dresden, Germany
A. Cavallaro, A. Aguadero
Department of Materials, Imperial College London
Prince Consort Road, London SW7 2BP, UK

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202400872>

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Similar short-circuit diffusion has been observed for a prototypical cathode material such as $\text{La}_{0.6}\text{Sr}_{0.4}\text{Co}_{0.2}\text{Fe}_{0.8}\text{O}_{3.8}$ (LSCF6428) and in acceptor (Ca)-doped LaCrO_3 in the form of ceramics.^[16–18] GB properties of Sr-doped LaCrO_3 (LSCr) thin films have been the subject of a recent publication from our group.^[19] There, we used novel isotope exchange-atom probe tomography (IE-APT) method for directly observing fast oxygen diffusion pathways along the GBs. Unprecedented 3D and sub-nm resolution for the study of local oxygen kinetics has been achieved by IE-APT, providing the framework for accessing previously concealed aspects of local GB chemistries and related effects.^[20,21] Notably, lanthanum chromite assumes relevance in the SOC field owing to the very wide redox stability combined with a predominantly electronic character for electrical conductivity, which makes it well-suited, e.g., for interconnects.^[22,23] Moreover, doping of the B-site promotes a remarkable activity toward hydrogen oxidation reaction (HOR).^[24]

Despite these advancements, the application of thin films as SOC electrode components is still in its infancy and has been limited to a few specific examples. Ceria-based dense films, fabricated by physical methods (down to 200 nm thick), have been implemented as electrode-electrolyte interlayers, effectively preventing the formation of secondary phases by blocking cation diffusion.^[25,26] More recently, the use of thin film nanocomposites as functional interlayers has been also proposed, with the purpose of combining interface stabilization and enhancement of the cathode activity.^[27,28] Buzi et al. have developed a self-assembled thin film nanostructure based on $(\text{La,Sr})\text{CoO}_3$ (LSC) and Sm-doped ceria (SDC) and successfully applied it as a full cathode in a reversible SOC, achieving good long-term performance and a remarkable decrease in critical raw material utilization.^[29] Additional examples of use of thin films in SOCs are related to sub-micrometer devices based on microelectromechanical systems (microSOFs) having potential application as portable energy devices.^[30] There, impressive performance of up to 2.5 W cm^{-2} at 650°C was reported.^[31] Despite these early examples, it becomes however apparent that the full capabilities of nanostructured and interface-dominated thin films for SOC engineering are yet to be unlocked.

Herein, we demonstrate the use of GB-dominated thin films of LSCr as electrode layers for SOCs. We carry out a detailed fundamental analysis of the microstructural and chemical characteristics of LSCr GBs and relate them to the strongly enhanced local oxygen transport properties of GBs, which exhibit a local increase of up to 4 orders of magnitude in diffusivity and surface exchange coefficient. We validate the use of nanocrystalline dense LSCr thin films ($\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$) as an electrochemically active component for both ORR and HOR. Finally, we carry out the proof of principle for a symmetric thin film electrode SOC that uses $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ as both air and hydrogen electrodes and show that reversible oper-

ation of the feeding gases can be exploited for promoting further enhancement of the electrode kinetics.

2. Results and Discussion

The structural and electrochemical properties of GBs in 10% Sr-doped LSCr have been assessed by direct comparison between $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and epitaxial (LSCr_{epi}) thin films ($\approx 40 \text{ nm}$ thick). The two microstructures have been obtained under the same fabrication conditions utilizing different substrates, namely Gd-doped ceria (CGO)-buffered sapphire (0001) or YSZ (h00) for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and SrTiO_3 (001) for LSCr_{epi} . Note that the use of two different substrates for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ was necessary for the different characterization techniques employed – cf. later in the text. The successful fabrication of the two microstructures becomes clear by comparing the XRD patterns (Figure 1), with $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ (on sapphire – Figure 1a) showing (hk0) and (00l) reflections, whereas LSCr_{epi} exhibits perfect overlap between film and substrate peaks along the (00l) reflections (Figure 1b). The thickness fringes around the (002) peak for LSCr_{epi} (Figure 1b inset) indicate high-quality layer-by-layer growth. No secondary phase outgrowths are detected according to top-view AFM analyses (panels (c) and (d) for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and LSCr_{epi} , respectively). The surface topography for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ (Figure 1c) is typical of nanocrystalline columnar films,^[11] with an approximate grain size $\approx 35 \text{ nm}$ as resulting from image analysis. Please refer to Figure S1 (Supporting Information) for characterization of $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ on YSZ.

The presence of a high GB density in $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ is expected to bring along important changes in the defect chemical environment of the film, as highlighted by a number of recent studies on poly- and nano-crystalline MIEC systems.^[32] In LSM films and LSCF ceramics, for example, deviations in the A/B cation ratio have been highlighted in the GB region, together with a depletion of the oxygen concentration.^[13,18] The chemistry of LSCr films has been assessed by means of complementary techniques including transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and positron annihilation lifetime spectroscopy (PALS). Results from TEM characterization on $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ are shown in Figure 2. In panel (a), showing a low magnification cross-section TEM image of the film and substrate areas, one can appreciate the ordered columnar structure of the film fabricated on top of CGO-YSZ. Fast Fourier transform (FFT) is reported in Figure S2 (Supporting Information), highlighting 10° – 15° tilting angle between grains. As a result of the small tilting angle, the GBs consist in a regular array of misfit dislocations with ≈ 10 atoms spacing, as reported in Figure 2b (Fourier filtering of the GB region reported in the inset). This type of GB has been previously observed in thin films.^[13] Chemical analysis of a GB region, carried out by electron-energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) linescan, is shown in Figure 2c. The linescan was acquired along the arrow indicated in the TEM micrograph of Figure 2d, crossing one GB. The area around the GB (vertical line in Figure 2c) exhibits a slight deviation in the cationic profile (Cr depletion in green in Figure 2d). Unlike similar systems,^[13,18] changes in the O signal (orange) across the GB are negligible within the instrumental resolution and dependent on the specific GB considered. Please refer to Figure S3 (Supporting Information) for the EELS analysis of a different GB, showing enhancement of La signal and O depletion. Interestingly, clear stoichiometry changes between the

A. Aguadero
Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid (ICMM-CSIC)
C/Sor Juana Inés de la Cruz 3, Madrid 28049, Spain
A. Tarancon
ICREA
23 Passeig Lluís Companys, Barcelona 08010, Spain

Figure 1. XRD and AFM characterization for LSCr thin films. a) XRD $\theta/2\theta$ full scan for LSCr_{nano}. In the inset, the high-resolution scan around the (110) LSCr peak is shown, with signal from LSCr_{nano} (110) peak appearing as a shoulder of the CGO (200) peak. b) XRD $\theta/2\theta$ full scan for LSCr_{epi}, with high resolution scan around the (001) LSCr peak in the inset. c,d) AFM micrographs for LSCr_{nano} (root mean square roughness $R_{ms} \approx 1.84$ nm) and LSCr_{epi} ($R_{ms} \approx 2.69$ nm).

different grains can be observed, as can be seen in the La profile step (blue) showing a sudden drop in concentration when crossing the GB. These observations indicate that LSCr_{nano} films are chemically inhomogeneous (i.e., A/B not constant) not just at the GB level (Cr depletion), but also depending on the region (grain) under consideration. Such a conclusion is in agreement with a previous study from our group on LSCr_{nano} by APT, where strong inhomogeneities in the A/B ratio for regions with width of ≈ 20 nm were observed.^[19] Please refer to a previous publication from our group for planar view high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM) images of LSCr_{nano}, highlighting a regular GB distribution with a grain size ≈ 35 nm.^[19]

PALS is capable of precisely probing the type and relative concentration of defects with nanometric depth resolution, by relating the lifetime of positrons in neutral and negatively charged open volumes (vacancies and vacancy associates, vacancy clusters, etc.) with their size.^[33,34] The results of depth (z)-resolved positron lifetime spectra analysis for LSCr_{nano} and LSCr_{epi} are reported in **Figure 3**. Two ranges of characteristic annihilation times are found (τ_{d1} and τ_{d2} – **Figure 3a,b**, respectively), corresponding to group of defects (d_1 and d_2) with distinctively different positron annihilation times.^[35] The relative intensities (defect concentrations – I_i) for d_1 and d_2 are reported in panels (c) and

(d), respectively. One can observe that, while LSCr_{epi} is predominantly characterized by isolated cationic defects (Cr vacancies – V_{Cr}''' having $I_{d1} \approx 60\%$), the crystallographic disorder introduced by GBs determines the presence of a rich population of defect associates in LSCr_{nano}. It is worth mentioning that, even if PALS is not sensitive to isolated oxygen vacancies (V_O^\bullet) owing to the positive charge, this type of defect can be detected by PALS as a defect complex. Here, V_O^\bullet and B-site vacancy complexes (V_{Cr}''') are found with relative concentration $I_{d1} \approx 60\%$. A high relative intensity of large complexes ($V_A + V_O^\bullet + V_{Cr}'''$, $I_{d2} \approx 40\%$) is also observed in LSCr_{nano}, suggesting a high-concentration of oxygen vacancies (non-diluted scenario).^[3] The observed reduced enthalpy of oxygen vacancy formation in LSCr_{nano} can be associated with the presence of a regular array of dislocations at GBs (cf. **Figure 2b**). In SrTiO₃ for example,^[36] the dislocation core was found to be strongly oxygen depleted whereas, in LSM, an accumulation of oxygen vacancies at space-charge zones around dislocations may be expected according to recent studies.^[6] This observation is arguably key for the observed GB-induced oxygen transport properties of LSCr_{nano}, as detailed next. Curiously, for both films a certain inhomogeneity is found, as the sub-surface region (≈ 10 nm) is characterized by larger defects (higher τ_{d1} and τ_{d2}), irrespective of the microstructure. Please refer to **Figure S4** (Supporting

Figure 2. a) High Resolution TEM cross-section of LSCr_{nano}. b) FFT transform of the GB region shown in the inset. c) EELS linescan along the blue arrow indicated in panel d), which is dedicated to a scanning TEM image of a single GB.

Information) for Doppler broadening variable energy positron annihilation spectroscopy and average positron lifetime analyses, confirming the higher defect concentration for LSCr_{nano} and a non-monotonic depth profile.

In order to obtain a precise quantification of the effects of GB-induced local chemical changes on the oxygen exchange rate of LSCr films, ¹⁸O isotope exchange depth profiling has been carried out using time-of-flight secondary ion emission spectroscopy (ToF-SIMS).^[36] While in a previous publication from our group we had focused on comparing ToF-SIMS with IE-ATP using LSCr as a model system,^[19] in this work we carried out a

temperature-dependent comprehensive analysis of oxygen diffusivity (D^*) and surface exchange coefficient (k^q) in LSCr_{nano} and LSCr_{epi}, as shown in Figure 4, panels a and b, respectively. The depth-resolved ¹⁸O fraction for LSCr_{nano} after isotope exchange presents a complex profile (Figure 4a – dotted lines). For the lowest temperature considered (540 °C), one can observe the presence of a single tail in the depth profile ($z \approx 10$ nm) followed by a step at the LSCr/CGO interface ($z \approx 40$ nm – vertical dotted line in Figure 4a), which are typical signatures of fast GB diffusion. This observation is in line with our previous investigation based on IE-APT.^[19] For higher temperatures, an

Figure 3. PALS defect analysis for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and LSCr_{epi} . Depth-resolved positron lifetime for small ($d1$ – panel a) and large ($d2$ – panel b) defect types. The horizontal lines and grey areas represent the expected positron lifetimes of different defect states, retrieved in analogy with ab-initio calculations for the STO structure.^[35] c,d) Relative intensities for $d1$ (c) and $d2$ (d). The dotted vertical line in the panels indicates the nominal position of the film/substrate interface.

additional tail with higher slope appears at $z \approx 25$ nm close to the LSCr/CGO interface. We ascribe this feature to compositional inhomogeneities in the grain interior (i.e., the portion of the grain having the electrochemical behavior of the bulk),^[37] in qualitative agreement with TEM and PALS results (cf. Figures 2 and 3). The experimental data were iteratively simulated by finite element modeling (FEM) using a 2D geometry for quantification of D^* and k^q (grain size = 35 nm, GB width = 1 nm – panels (b), (c) and (d) for fitting of 540, 590 and 640 °C exchange temperatures, respectively).^[19,20] In Figure 4a, the extracted 1D profiles of the best fits are reported as continuous lines. These have been obtained considering 4 free parameters (D_{g}^* , k_{g}^q and D_{gb}^* , k_{gb}^q for grain interior and GBs, respectively), in general agree-

ment with literature.^[15,38] Importantly, while this model is capable of precisely analyzing the low temperature profile (540 °C), a more complex one is necessary to capture the ^{18}O profile at the LSCr/CGO interface for higher exchange temperatures. In Figure S5 (Supporting Information) we propose a FEM geometry that accurately describes this additional feature by adding a region with lower D_{g}^* at the LSCr/CGO interface region. A striking difference in the ^{18}O decay profile can be appreciated between $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and LSCr_{epi} , with a much shorter penetration depth for the oxygen isotope in the absence of GBs (Figure 4e). Here, the experimental data (dotted lines) can be easily fitted using 1-D Crank solution to Fick's law (continuous lines), typical of bulk diffusion.

Figure 4. a) 1D ^{18}O fraction experimental profiles (dotted lines) for different temperatures and resulting best fitting (continuous lines) for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$. b) 2D FEM fitting for 540 °C, c) 590 °C, and d) 640 °C exchange temperatures. e) 1D ^{18}O fraction experimental profiles (dotted lines) for different temperatures and resulting best fitting (continuous lines) for LSCr_{epi} .

The GB kinetics are characterized by a $\approx 3\text{--}4$ orders of magnitude higher diffusivity and surface exchange coefficient of the GB with respect to the grain interior (e.g., $D_{\text{gb}}^* \approx 7 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{\text{gb}}^q \approx 1.3 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, $D_{\text{g}}^* \approx 1 \times 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{\text{g}}^q \approx 8.2 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ at 640 °C), as reported in **Figure 5** showing the diffusivity (panel a) and surface exchange coefficient (panel b) as a function of the inverse temperature. This observation is in line with previous reports on LSM – where high diffusivity was found in correspondence with low-angle GBs and dislocations^[13,40] and is in contrast to some other perovskites (e.g., $(\text{La}, \text{Sr})\text{CoO}_3$ or SrTiO_3), showing slower diffusion along extended defects.^[5,41] With respect to LSM however, here even higher GB oxygen kinetics is highlighted – **Figure 5**. Notably, the resulting D_{bulk}^* and k_{bulk}^q obtained for LSCr_{epi} are similar to D_{g}^* and k_{g}^q for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ (cf. **Figure 5a,b**), confirming the robustness of the analysis. The quality of the FEM-based simulations is further corroborated by the similar values obtained for the average k^q (k_{av}^q) derived by SIMS and the ones obtained by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (k_{EIS}^q) – cf. **Figure 5b** and later in the text. Note that some differences between k_{av}^q and k_{EIS}^q are to be expected given that two different substrates have been employed for SIMS (CGO-buffered sapphire) and EIS (CGO-buffered YSZ). As far as the activation energies are concerned, the GBs are characterized by a much higher activation energy for both surface exchange ($E_{\text{a,surf}}^{\text{GB}} = 2.7 \pm 0.1 \text{ eV}$) and diffusivity ($E_{\text{a,diff}}^{\text{GB}} = 2.6 \pm 0.1 \text{ eV}$), in contrast to the grain interior ($E_{\text{a,surf}}^{\text{g}} = 0.8 \pm 0.1 \text{ eV}$ and

$E_{\text{a,diff}}^{\text{g}} = 0.6 \pm 0.1 \text{ eV}$). Interestingly, recent studies by Boegers et al. on a related system (LSM) have associated $E_{\text{a,diff}}^{\text{GB}} > E_{\text{a,diff}}^{\text{int}}$ to fast oxygen kinetics at GBs due oxygen vacancy accumulation in space-charge regions (rather than to enhanced vacancy mobility at the GB core).^[6] Note that the range of values for E_{a}^{g} from $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and $E_{\text{a}}^{\text{bulk}}$ from LSCr_{epi} is typically associated to the enthalpy of pure migration for perovskites,^[17,39] suggesting negligible contribution from the vacancy formation enthalpy.^[40] This interesting finding is tentatively attributed to a sluggish temperature dependence for oxygen vacancy concentration within the bulk of LSCr, in agreement with the predominantly electronic character of conduction in the material due to very low oxygen off-stoichiometry. It is noteworthy that the occurrence of fast oxygen diffusion is often associated with the presence of regular mesostructures capable of strongly altering the local functionalities. This was found here or in LSM films (dislocation array),^[13] but also, e.g., in the case of Pr_2NiO_4 single crystals, where long-range domain ordering (translational periodicity 70 Å) was found to be linked to a surprisingly high chemical diffusion coefficient of $D^* = 6.3 \times 10^{-11} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at room temperature.^[44] Interestingly, the observed chemical composition differences between different grains in $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ (cf. **Figure 2c**), together with the complex phase diagram of the LSCr – involving orthorhombic together with rhombohedral phases – add a rare structural complexity for the formation of twin domains in the system under consideration.^[45]

Figure 5. Temperature dependence for oxygen diffusivity a) and surface exchange coefficient b) for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and LSCr_{epi} compared to references. The activation energies are reported next to each linear fit. The legend is defined as follows: A = $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ GB – SIMS; B = $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ grain interior – SIMS; C = $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ average – SIMS; D = $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ GB – APT;^[19] E = $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ grain interior – APT;^[19] F = k^0_{EIS} ; G = LSCr_{epi} (bulk); H = $\text{La}_{0.78}\text{Ca}_{0.22}\text{CrO}_3$ ceramic, bulk;^[16] I = $\text{La}_{0.78}\text{Ca}_{0.22}\text{CrO}_3$ ceramic, GB;^[16] J = LSM_{bulk} – SIMS;^[20] K = LSM_{gb} – SIMS.^[20]

The electrochemical properties of $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ under realistic conditions for SOC operation have been tested by EIS on films deposited on top of CGO-YSZ (Figure 6). Exemplary Nyquist plots, retrieved at 700 °C, are shown in Figure 6a. The impedance spectra measured in air atmosphere (black squares) is characterized by an almost perfect semicircle and can be fit with a single ZARC element. The absence of a 45° Warburg diffusion element in the high frequency range indicates that resistance to oxygen diffusion is not dominant, i.e., oxygen incorporation is limited in these structures by surface exchange.^[41] This is in agreement with SIMS analysis (cf. Figure 4), which showed that GBs offer a pathway for fast oxygen diffusion in $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$. The resulting area-specific resistance under open-circuit voltage conditions (ASR_{OCV}) at 700 °C is $\approx 63 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$. In order to test the suitability of $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ as a symmetric electrode layer, we also measured

EIS in a symmetric hydrogen atmosphere (100% H_2).^[42] One can observe that $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ presents a certain activity toward HOR ($\text{ASR}_{\text{OCV}} \approx 84.5 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ at 700 °C – blue circles). The measured ASR_{OCV} is however higher in hydrogen than in air – despite ORR being typically more sluggish than HOR – highlighting the effectiveness of LSCr engineering through GBs for oxygen exchange. This finding is also related to the higher activation energy for the ASR_{OCV} in air with respect to hydrogen (2.33 ± 0.11 eV and 1.21 ± 0.02 eV, respectively – Figure 6b). The temperature dependence of the ASR allows comparison with state-of-the-art (SoA) air and hydrogen electrode layers, whose performance is reported in Figure 6b for dense thin films to provide direct comparison. Consistently with SIMS data (cf. Figure 5), $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ overcomes the performance of dense LSM nanocrystalline films (green line).^[43] HOR performance is compared to

Figure 6. a) Exemplary impedance spectra (700 °C) for LSCr_{nano} in hydrogen (blue circles) and air atmospheres (black squares), and for LT-LSCr_{nano} (grey circles). The fitting curves (1 ZARC element) are reported as red lines. b) Temperature dependence of the ASR. The data are compared with reference LSM films,^[43] SDC (our labs), and LSCM (our labs). c) Current density as a function of electrode overpotential for LSCr_{nano} and LSC (500 °C).^[29]

20%Sm-doped ceria (SDC – orange) and La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}Cr_{0.5}Mn_{0.5}O₃ (LSCM – purple).^[24,44] Remarkably, LSCr_{nano} exhibits similar activity with respect to LSCM – despite B-site doping being considered essential for HOR activity in bulk chromite –^[24,45] suggesting GB engineering to be effective even for promoting hydrogen oxidation. An even more meaningful comparison with SoA air electrode materials is provided in Figure 6c, where LSCr_{nano}

is matched against one of the best performing cathode materials used for SOC applications – namely La_{0.8}Sr_{0.2}CoO₃ (LSC) –^[46] in terms of current density (*j*) as a function of the overpotential (*η*). While measurements in OCV conditions (cf. Figure 6b) measure the resistance of oxygen oxidation and reduction reactions, the application of an electric bias allows assessing far-from-equilibrium situations in which the reverse current density becomes negligible.^[47] These measurements are therefore better suited in order to describe the real behavior of an electrode under SOC operation conditions, taking also into account the changes in point defect concentration occurring when an overpotential (i.e., the difference between the applied bias and the potential drop at the electrolyte – cf. experimental) is applied.^[29,48] Despite the large differences in ASR_{OCV} between LSCr_{nano} (≈12400 Ω cm⁻² at 500 °C – cf. Figure S6, Supporting Information) and LSC (≈605 Ω cm⁻²), LSCr_{nano} undergoes strong activation under both negative (cathodic) and positive (anodic) biases so that, for high potential, we observed slightly higher current density than for LSC. For example, the ASR values, e.g., for *η* = -0.27 V are 24.5 Ω cm⁻² for LSCr_{nano} and 31.5 Ω cm⁻² for LSC (Figure S6, Supporting Information). A qualitatively similar situation is encountered for anodic potential (i.e., oxygen evolution reaction), with LSCr_{nano} providing lower polarization resistance than LSC for *η* > 0.16.

In Supplementary Information, results on the structural (XRD, SEM – Figure S7, Supporting Information), surface (by X-Ray photoemission spectroscopy – XPS, Figure S8, Supporting Information), and electrochemical (EIS – Figure S9, Supporting Information) characterization of amorphous LSCr films (LT-LSCr_{nano}), deposited at 500 °C, are reported. There, we observed that decreasing the fabrication temperature leads to even lower ASR (≈20 Ω cm⁻² at 700 °C and decreased energy of activation (1.68±0.02 eV), in agreement with previous investigations on related MIEC perovskites.^[49–51] We ascribe this finding to the expected maximized GB density in LT-LSCr_{nano}. Note also that LT-LSCr_{nano} is characterized by higher A/B and Sr_{surf}/Sr_{bulk} ratios according to XPS (Figure S8, Supporting Information). This interesting finding is in apparent contrast with literature reports indicating higher activity for B-site rich surface and a detrimental effect of Sr_{surf}, suggesting that the electrochemical activity of GB-dominated materials may be less sensitive to surface composition.^[52]

The fundamental electrochemical characterization reported in Figure 6 confirms that LSCr_{nano} possesses a remarkable activity for ORR and HOR, compared to SoA model film materials. These findings motivated us to explore the behavior of LSCr_{nano} in a real SOFC system composed by symmetric dense LSCr_{nano} (including Au current collectors) and a single crystal YSZ electrolyte, which resulted in a power density of ≈9 mW cm⁻² at 10 mA cm⁻² and 750 °C (Figure 7a). Although this value may appear lower compared to what reported in literature for microSOFCs and SOC systems based on thin film electrodes,^[53,54] one should acknowledge the more fundamental approach undertaken by our work concerning in particular the use of a thick (500 μm) YSZ single crystal electrolyte. Considering the expected power loss at the electrolyte, the theoretical peak power density using a SoA thin film electrolyte for microSOFC (100 nm) reaches remarkable values >750 mW.^[55] Moreover, the IV curve reported in Figure 7a shows an open circuit voltage ≈0.93 V, suggesting imperfect

sealing. (Please note –Figure S10, Supporting Information) – no systematic change in the OCV is observed, i.e., a potential local T drift caused by leakage getting larger during the experiment can be ruled out). While the optimization of a full thin film microSOFC will be object of a dedicated study, the device fabricated represents a proof of concept for the applicability of GB engineered film electrodes in a real system. To the best of the authors' knowledge, our work also shows the first example of symmetric thin film SOFC operation with ceramic electrodes, which is enabled here by GB engineering. Unique to symmetric systems is the possibility to operate by reversing the feeding gases into the cell, providing the opportunity to mitigate electrode degradation processes, e.g. S or C poisoning or Sr segregation.^[56,57] We tested this possibility by carrying out a series of cycles by exchanging the feeding gases (synthetic air and humidified H_2) during ≈ 40 h SOFC operation in galvanostatic conditions (current of 2 and 4 mA cm^{-2} – cf. Figure S10, Supporting Information for voltage evolution). The results are reported in Figure 7 in terms of device power (measured at 4 mA cm^{-2} –Figure S10, Supporting Information for IV curves) and ASR (measured in OCV conditions between cycles), as shown in panels b and c, respectively. Comparing the initial values (index “i”) for the same gas configuration (“A” (grey box) or “B” (blue box)), one clearly observes an increase in the output power and a decrease of the ASR at each cycle. This improvement does not simply recover for the degradation observed during each cycle (cf. initial and final – values indexed by “f” – power and ASR values) but even determines a remarkable enhancement of the power (e.g., +54% between 1st and 2nd “A” configurations) and ASR decrease (-52% for the two “A” cycles). We tentatively ascribe this remarkable self-healing effect to the progressive establishment of a thermodynamic equilibrium at high temperatures (as opposed to off-equilibrium preparation conditions), possibly characterized by a surface composition (A/B ratio) with higher activity.^[43]

3. Conclusion

We investigated the local structural, chemical, and functional properties of fast-oxygen conducting grain boundaries in nanocrystalline $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{CrO}_3$ thin films, using a suite of advanced characterization techniques including high-resolution TEM, PALS, and IEDP-SIMS. Grain-boundary doping promotes the formation of a high concentration of oxygen vacancies, as shown by PALS analysis, and determines local cationic inhomogeneities both at the grain boundary level and between different grains as revealed by HR-TEM. As a consequence, nanocrystalline $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{CrO}_3$ exhibits interface-dominated behavior, by which the expected electronic character of bulk $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{CrO}_3$ is turned into mixed ionic-electronic conducting, with remarkable activity toward oxygen reduction reaction ($\approx 24.5 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-2}$ at 500 °C under cathodic polarization). As a proof of concept, we fabricated a symmetric SOC cell incorporating nanocrystalline $\text{La}_{0.9}\text{Sr}_{0.1}\text{CrO}_3$ dense films as both air and fuel electrode. The cell was operated for ≈ 40 h with alternating feeding gases, obtaining remarkable performance enhancement due to electrode self-healing enabled by reversible operation. This study highlights the potential of grain boundary engineering for developing new electrode materials with enhanced perfor-

Figure 7. a) Current-voltage and power-voltage curves for symmetric SOC with $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ electrodes (750 °C). b) Power at 4 mA cm^{-2} and ASR_{OCV} recorded at the beginning (“i”) and end (“f”) of galvanostatic steps during reversible operation. The configurations are marked with grey (configuration A, i.e., air on top chamber compartment) and blue (B, air on bottom chamber compartment).

mance and demonstrates their direct applicability in real energy systems.

4. Experimental Section

LSCr thin films were fabricated by large-area pulsed laser deposition method (PVD Systems – PLD 5000) equipped with a 248 nm KrF excimer laser (Lambda Physics—COMPex PRO 205) on top of single crystal sapphire (0001), YSZ (100) and STO (100) (Crystal GmbH). A buffer layer of CGO was deposited on top of sapphire and YSZ substrates to prevent reaction with the films (in the case of YSZ) and to allow for a more precise assessment of the GB electrochemical characteristics by IEDP-SIMS (in the case of sapphire). The choice of different substrates for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ was dictated by the different electrochemical characterization methods: inert sapphire for IEDP-SIMS and YSZ electrolyte for EIS. The films were deposited by ablating homemade stoichiometric targets, using an oxygen background pressure of 0.007 mbar, target-to-substrate distance 90 mm, laser fluency 1.1 J cm^{-2} , frequency 10 Hz. The deposition temperature was 750 °C for $\text{LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$ and LSCr_{epi} and 500 °C for $\text{LT-LSCr}_{\text{nano}}$.

XRD characterization was carried out using a Bruker-D8 Advance instrument using $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation with a nickel filter and a Lynx Eye detector. AFM was performed with equipment provided by Park System Corp. Auriga Zeiss equipment was used for SEM. For TEM observation, cross-sectional samples of the thin films were prepared by Focused Ion Beam (FIB) in a Thermofischer Scios after sputtering the surface with gold. The High-Resolution TEM (HRTEM) images of the lamellae were acquired in a JEOL JEM 2010F and the EELS profiles were obtained in a JEOL NeoARM, both working at 200 kV accelerating voltage, at the CCITUB (ICTS ELEMCI

node in Barcelona). Image treatment and EELS analysis were performed using Gatan Microscopy Suite Software. EELS quantification was obtained using the conventional Egerton method included in the software. Variable energy positron annihilation lifetime spectroscopy (VEPALS) measurements were performed at the Mono-energetic Positron Source (MePS) beamline at HZDR, Germany.^[58] A CeBr₃ scintillator detector coupled to a Hamamatsu R13089-100 photomultiplier tube (PMT) was chosen for gamma photons detection. The signals were processed by the SPDevices ADQ14DC-2X digitizer (14-bit vertical resolution and 2GS/s horizontal resolution).^[59] The overall time resolution of the measurement system was ≈0.250 ns and the overall statistic of at least 10⁷ counts was acquired. A typical lifetime spectrum N(t), the absolute value of the time derivative of the positron decay spectrum, is described by

$$N(t) = R(t) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{k+1} \frac{I_i}{\tau_i} e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_i}} + \text{Background} \quad (1)$$

where k is the number of different defect types contributing to the positron trapping, which are related to k + 1 components in the spectra with the individual lifetimes τ_i and intensities I_i ($\sum I_i = 1$). The instrument resolution function R(t) is a sum of two Gaussian functions with distinct intensities and relative shifts both depending on the positron implantation energy. It was determined by the measurement and analysis of a reference sample, i.e., amorphous Ytria-stabilized zirconia (YSZ), which exhibited a single well-known lifetime component. The background was negligible, hence fixed to zero.

All the spectra were deconvoluted using a non-linear least-squares fitting method, minimized by the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm, employed within the fitting software package PALSfit into 2 major lifetime components.^[60] They directly evidence localized annihilation at 2 different defect types (sizes; $\tau d1$ and $\tau d2$). Their relative intensities scale typically with concentration of each defect type. In general, positron lifetime increases with defects size and open volume size. The positron lifetime and its intensity have been probed in function of positron implantation energy E_p , which was recalculated to the mean implantation depth (z). The average positron lifetime τ_{av} is defined as $\tau_{av} = \sum_i \tau_i \cdot I_i$.

Doppler broadening variable energy positron annihilation spectroscopy (DB-VEPAS) measurements have been conducted at the apparatus for in situ defect analysis (AIDA) of the slow positron beamline (SPONSOR).^[61,62] Positrons have been accelerated and monoenergetically implanted into samples in the range between $E_p = 0.05$ and 12 keV, which allows for depth profiling. A mean positron implantation depth was approximated using a simple material density (ρ) dependent Equation (2).^[63]

$$\langle z \rangle [nm] = \frac{36}{\rho [g \cdot cm^{-3}]} E_p^{1.62} [keV] \quad (2)$$

Implanted into a solid, positrons lose their kinetic energy due to thermalization and after short diffusion annihilate in delocalized lattice sites or localize in vacancy like defects and interfaces emitting usually two anti-collinear 511keV gamma photons once they meet electrons. Since at the annihilation site thermalized positrons have very small momentum compared to the electrons, a broadening of the 511 keV line is observed mostly due to momentum of the electrons. This broadening is characterized by two distinct parameters S and W defined as a fraction of the annihilation line in the middle (511 ± 0.93 keV) and outer regions (508.56 ± 0.35 and 513.44 ± 0.35 keV), respectively. The total area below the curve, which is utilized for normalization of both parameters, is 511 ± 16.24 keV. The S-parameter is a fraction of positrons annihilating with low momentum valence electrons and represents vacancy type defects and their concentration. The W-parameter approximates the overlap of the positron wavefunction with high momentum core electrons, and gives a fingerprint of the local atomic chemistry at the annihilation site.

For IEPD-SIMS, the surfaces of the films were cleaned with pure ethanol and acetone before the oxygen isotope exchange. Initially, the samples were annealed in 200 mbar of pure oxygen (99.999%) with ¹⁸O₂ at its

natural isotopic abundance. The exchange chamber was then evacuated and refilled with ≈90% ¹⁸O₂-enriched gas (200 mbar). After the exchange, the samples were quenched to room temperature. The exchange was carried out at 639, 590, and 540 °C for 1803, 2026, and 2081 s, respectively. LSCr_{nano} and LSCr_{epi} were treated simultaneously to minimize experimental error. The ¹⁸O diffusion profiles were retrieved using a TOF-SIMS 5 instrument (ION-TOF GmbH, Münster, Germany). For negative ion analysis, a liquid metal bismuth gun (LMIG) with a 25 keV Bi⁺ primary ion beam was rastered over the sample surface, and secondary ions were detected in burst alignment mode. A secondary 2 keV Cs⁺ ion beam was used for depth profile analysis, with a 50 μ m × 50 μ m analysis area and a 150 μ m × 150 μ m sputtering area.

IEPD-SIMS profiles were fitting using a 2D FEM model using COMSOL Multiphysics using the "Transport of diluted species" model. The model geometry has grain size of 35 nm and GB width of 1 nm, in agreement with the TEM and APT data.^[19] A convective-type boundary equation was set for the free surface (oxygen incorporation), while zero flux was imposed on the other surfaces. A uniform initial tracer fraction of 0.002 was set to simulate the natural isotope background concentration. Time dependent Fick's second law of diffusion was numerically solved. Simulations were performed iteratively to find the set of oxygen transport properties that better fit the experimental data.

The XPS experiments were carried out in ESFOSCAN at the CCITUB (Barcelona), an equipment based on the PHI VersaProbe 4 instrument from Physical Electronics (ULVAC-PHI). Measurements have been done with a monochromatic focused X-ray source (Aluminium Kalfa line of 1486.6 eV) calibrated using the 3d5/2 line of Ag with a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 0.6 eV. The area analyzed was a circle of 100 microns in diameter, and the resolution selected for the spectra was 224 eV Pass Energy and 0.8 eV/step for the general spectra and 27 eV Pass Energy and 0.1 eV/ step for high resolution spectra of the selected elements. A combination of a low-energy electron gun (less than 10 eV) and a low-energy Argon ion gun (less than 100 eV) was used to discharge the sample when necessary. All measurements were performed in an ultra-high vacuum (UHV) chamber at a pressure between 5 × 10⁻¹⁰ and 5 × 10⁻⁹ Torr.

Electrochemical characterization was carried out on a commercial ProboStat (NorECS AS) station, inside a high-temperature vertical tube furnace. EIS measurements under symmetric atmospheres were conducted by a Novocontrol spectrometer (NOVOCONTROL Technologies GmbH & Co. KG) using synthetic air or humidified H₂ (3% H₂O) on symmetric cell. The oscillating voltage was 50 mV, with frequency range 1 to 100 MHz. Full cells were measured in a setup by Huber Scientific using a Parstat 2273 spectrometer. Sealing was obtained using compressive sealant or Ceramabond (Aremco) paste. Bias experiments were performed in a Linkam station on asymmetric cells with Ag paste counter-electrodes. Measurements consisted in 2 min chronoamperometric test, followed by an impedance measurement under the same bias using oscillating voltage of 30 mV. The overpotential of the thin film electrode was then calculated using $\eta = (V_{\text{applied}} - I \times R)$ where R is the sum of the resistances associated with YSZ and porous Ag as stemming from impedance.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in [Zenodo] at [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14535944>], reference number [14535944].

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